

Disruptive Climate Protests Against Companies: Analyzing Customer Perceptions in an Experimental Setting

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Abstract

In response to insufficient progress on carbon neutrality commitments, climate activism is increasingly targeting companies—both oil companies and the banks that finance their activity. Drawing on Attribution Theory, this research investigates how protest extremity (moderate vs. disruptive) and target type (oil companies vs. banks funding oil projects) influence perceived corporate agency and consumer behavior. In Study 1, a moderated mediation model revealed that moderate protests were more effective than disruptive ones, particularly when aimed at banks. Disruptive protests reduce perceived corporate agency and responsibility, thereby lowering consumers' intentions to switch providers. In Study 2, we manipulated the bank's role in exacerbating climate change (direct vs. indirect), but this framing did not significantly affect customer perceptions—suggesting that protest extremity, rather than target type, is the primary driver lowering perceived agency and switching intentions. Implications for climate activism strategies and corporate reputation management are discussed.

Keywords: *corporate agency, climate activism, consumer behavior, attribution theory, reputation management*

1. Introduction

Despite the growing trend of corporations setting carbon neutrality goals for 2050 (Erb et al., 2022), there is little evidence that companies committing to such climate targets are actually reducing their emissions as promised (Dahlmann et al., 2019). The plans of fossil fuel companies in particular have been shown to be incompatible with the targets set by the Paris Agreement (Noor, 2024). In response to this lack of progress in changing corporate trajectories, both North America and Europe have experienced a surge in climate protests. Activists demanding action on the climate crisis have used a myriad of tactics, such as throwing soup on famous paintings (Davis, 2022), interrupting sports events (Golen, 2024), and vandalizing office buildings of target companies (Bautzer, 2024), among many other actions.

Climate activism is a diverse force that seeks to mobilize people to collectively engage in efforts to pressure economic and political actors, to address climate change impacts (Fisher & Nasrin, 2021). The “diversity of tactics” (Brown, 2023) employed by activists—such as media advocacy, lawsuits, demonstrations, sit-ins, and blockades—have led to significant victories for the environmental movement, including investments in clean energy (Gustafson et al., 2020), fossil fuel divestment (Mitchell, 2024), cancelling the construction of nuclear power plants (Piazza & Perretti, 2020), and obstructing extractive projects (Temper et al., 2015). The partial successes of climate activists have not only been achieved through diverse tactics, but also through the adoption of a stepwise escalation strategy (Brown, 2023), where actions become more extreme, as governments and businesses remain unresponsive to activism at moderate levels.

In contrast to disruptive protests, moderate protests are often portrayed favorably by the media and avoid delegitimization (Stern et al., 1999). Still, stepwise escalation is often deemed necessary, mainly because moderate protests—such as holding banners during demonstrations—have long shown a limited impact: at best, activists end up bargaining with politicians and industry over the extent of “acceptable” environmental harm (Foreman, 1993, p. 17).

Disruptive actions against companies are not only more effective in negotiating the demands of protesters (Chenoweth & Stephan, 2011), but also tend to attract greater media attention (Ali & Gill, 2022). However, this increased visibility might come at the expense of alienating the general public (Badullovich et al., 2024; Davis, 2022; Feinberg et al., 2020). This raises a strategic dilemma for activists: should they prioritize moderate protests, which are generally less likely to provoke public backlash but receive limited media coverage, or should they pursue disruptive protests that attract media attention but risk negative public opinion? Moreover, from a corporate reputation management perspective, while disruptive protests may appear to pose a greater public relations threat, moderate protests may ultimately be more effective in reshaping public perception and undermining customer loyalty. Although seemingly counterintuitive, this outcome is theoretically plausible (e.g., Feinberg et al., 2020).

The present research examines the U.S. public’s response to two levels of climate protests against companies: moderate and disruptive protests. Across two studies, we compare changes in customer perceptions, caused by moderate and disruptive protests targeting companies responsible for the expansion of fossil fuel infrastructure. The U.S. public has encountered both types of protest in the media, for example, the high-profile non-violent disruptive actions that temporarily obstructed the construction of the Dakota Access Pipeline—a major oil pipeline in

the U.S. (Estes, 2024)—, and protests by the youth activists Sunrise Movement that blocked the House speaker’s office entrance (Noor, 2025).

The scope of the present research extends beyond protests only targeting oil companies, as climate activism has many targets, including financial institutions. Traditionally, banks have not been prominent in discussions about the energy transition. However, this is no longer the case, as it is obvious that they play a crucial role in financing oil projects, thereby exacerbating the climate crisis (Young & Thomas-Walters, 2024). For instance, activists spray-painted slogans on the Citigroup and Bank of America offices in New York, accusing them of being “climate criminals” (Bautzer, 2023).

To understand how activists’ tactics influence public perceptions and customer loyalty, we draw on Attribution Theory (Heider, 1958; Weiner, 1985), because it enables individuals to make causal ascriptions about an event or outcome. Specifically, we focus on how protest extremity shapes perceptions of corporate agency and attribution of responsibility to target companies. We analyze the effects of protests against two types of companies: oil companies involved in developing oil and gas projects, and banks that fund those projects. Accounting for the interplay between protest extremity and protest target reveals varying public reactions to climate protests, contributing to a better understanding of this complex phenomena and offering insights relevant to both climate activism and corporate reputation management.

2. Theoretical background and hypothesis development

2.1. Attribution Theory

Disruptive protests that involve emotional or physical damage are generally perceived negatively by observers compared to moderate protests (Feinberg et al., 2020). This negative perception can be understood through Attribution Theory (Heider, 1958; Weiner, 1985), which originates from Heider's (1944) seminal work on social perception and causal reasoning. According to Heider (1944), individuals construct causal explanations to make sense of their environment to maintain a sense of control over their circumstances.

Attribution Theory posits that people ascribe meaning to outcomes by attributing them to specific causes, which can be intrinsic, dispositional, extrinsic, or situational (Heider, 1944; Kelley, 1967; Weiner, 1985). Kelley (1973) expanded the theory by introducing a covariation model proposing that when individuals receive information from multiple sources, they assess whether a cause consistently covaries with its effects. If the cause is attributed to an individual's internal characteristics—such as personality, attitudes, or beliefs—it is classified as an internal attribution. Conversely, if the cause is linked to external factors, such as environmental conditions or situational influences, it is considered an external attribution (Kelley, 1973).

Attribution theory not only explains how individuals assign causes to behavior but also elucidates how these attributions influence subsequent reactions (Harvey et al., 2014). For instance, when an individual engages in malicious behavior, observers are more likely to react negatively if they attribute the behavior to the individual's disposition (e.g., personality) rather than to external circumstances (e.g., stress or a difficult day). A similar effect occurs in the opposite direction, where positive behavior is perceived more favorably when attributed to

intrinsic traits rather than external factors. This phenomenon arises because people tend to reward behaviors that appear internally driven rather than externally motivated.

In the context of environmental sustainability, attribution processes also shape consumer perceptions of corporate actions. Zou et al. (2015) apply attribution theory to determine that, for companies, the perception of culpability is shaped by past environmental behaviors, and the company's history of environmental harms or awards influences the way new events are interpreted. When consumers perceive that a company is deliberately harming the environment, such as prioritizing profit over sustainability or engaging in unethical business practices, they are more likely to form negative judgments based on dispositional attributions.

Prior work on attribution suggests that individuals tend to favor dispositional inferences over alternative explanations when interpreting an entity's behavior (Heider, 1958; Weiner, 1985). Building on Attribution Theory, we propose that disruptive protests against companies involved in expanding fossil fuel infrastructure may shift attributional focus away from corporate misconduct and towards activists themselves. Specifically, protest tactics seen as disruptive or confrontational, may trigger negative dispositional attributions about activists' motives—being irrational, aggressive, or attention-seeking. Consequently, this attributional pattern could result in negative perceptions of the activists, portraying their actions as unjustified or reckless rather than situational responses to systemic environmental harm caused by companies.

2.2. Disruptive protests' impacts on switching intentions

2.2.1 Protest extremity and protest target

From a semantic standpoint, protest extremity can be viewed as a continuum ranging from legal tactics to violence (Brown, 2023). Within this spectrum, we specifically focus on non-violent disruptive protests (i.e., civil disobedience), which aim to materially challenge a company's ability to contribute to the climate crisis. Moreover, disruption does not equate to destructive actions or property damage. Perfectly non-violent tactics such as boycotts and sit-ins can be effective if sustained over time because they can incur economic losses (e.g., loss of clients or temporarily shut down operations) to the sectors contributing to the climate crisis (Chenoweth & Stephan, 2011; Young & Thomas-Walters, 2024). For example, disruptive protests against the Atlantic Coast Pipeline on the U.S. East Coast significantly delayed the project and drove costs \$3.5 billion over the original budget, threatening the economic viability of the pipeline (Vogelsong, 2020). This led energy companies to withdraw from the entire project, ultimately resulting in its cancellation.

The recent impacts of climate change coincide with a new generation of climate activism that utilizes more disruptive tactics in order to garner media coverage and attention from policymakers. These protests have drawn public attention to environmental causes, but the cost of such media coverage remains unclear: while many studies found that disruptive protests tend to lead to negative sentiments toward the movement (Badullovich et al., 2024; Feinberg et al., 2020; Wasow, 2020), others found no evidence of confrontational protests backfiring and influencing climate change concerns (Brehm & Gruhl, 2024), with a recent longitudinal study even finding long-term positive effects on public support after the initial backlash diminishes

(Ostarek et al., 2024). These studies were mainly focused on individuals' stance towards the environmental movement in a general context.

However, to the best of our knowledge, no studies have examined how companies targeted by disruptive climate protests are perceived. Attribution Theory provides a theoretical framework to test the possibility that observers of disruptive protests may shift their stance and potentially develop positive sentiments toward the targeted companies. We also anticipate that companies with less apparent connections with the climate crisis—banks funding oil projects—are more insulated from the effects of disruptive protests than companies with more direct involvement in the climate crisis—oil companies.

2.2.2 Perceived Agency and Responsibility

Attribution theory of motivation suggests that different causal ascriptions lead to distinct motivational outcomes (Weiner, 1985). Fishman and Husman (2017) propose that attributions can be classified along three key dimensions: locus (whether the cause originates internally or externally), stability (whether the cause is enduring or temporary), and controllability (the extent to which the cause can be voluntarily altered). Prior applications of Attribution theory indicate that these dimensions influence individuals' evaluations of harmful acts. For example, Tamborini et al. (2018) found that when individuals attribute harmful behavior to external factors rather than internal dispositions, they tend to be more forgiving and accommodating of such actions. Similarly, Ginder et al. (2021) suggest that a company's corporate social responsibility (CSR) initiatives—encompassing both internal actions and external communications—influence how people assign responsibility. In particular, when there is a mismatch between a company's internal CSR efforts and its external messaging, it increases

the likelihood of attribution errors, thereby shaping the general public's ascription of responsibility (i.e., the process of assigning blame or credit for an outcome).

When it comes to ascription of responsibility, there is a growing consensus that companies should be held responsible for their misconduct through a stronger cosmopolitan agency, public engagement, and collective action (Vestergaard & Uldam, 2022). In real-world situations, responsibility involves how agents—i.e., companies—interact with each other and how others hold them accountable in responding to environmental concerns (Comyns et al., 2023). This becomes increasingly complex when consumers believe that “ought implies can”, or think that companies have a varied level of contribution and control on the way their business activities impact the environment: according to a poll of 1000 American adults by The Guardian (McGreal, 2021), 70% agreed that global warming was happening, and more than 60% believed that oil and gas companies were primarily responsible for it.

The ascription of responsibility process is inherently linked to the concept of corporate agency because, for responsibility to be ascribed, a company must be viewed as an agent capable of intentional action (Williams, 2019). In other words, the attribution of high responsibility to companies stems from the perception of their high agency. Therefore, we predict that when customers perceive companies as having a high agency, their perceived ascription of responsibility increases, as customers perceive the company as having control of their actions when they develop or fund a new oil and gas project. Drawing on the rationale outlined above, we propose the following hypotheses:

H1: Perceived corporate agency will be higher for the oil company operating oil and gas projects than for the bank funding them.

H2: The effect of company type (oil company vs. bank funding oil) on perceived corporate agency is moderated by protest extremity, with perceived corporate agency diverging more between company types as protest extremity changes from moderate to disruptive.

H3: Perceived corporate agency positively predicts ascription of responsibility for climate change-related harm.

When a company is viewed as an agent capable of intentional action, it must adhere to high ethical standards in the context of environmental stewardship. Ginder et al. (2021) found that consumers were more likely to purchase from companies driven by internal CSR motives rather than external, profit-driven motives. These findings align with those of Valenzuela et al. (2010), who found that a firm's ethical reputation significantly influences customer retention and brand loyalty. Thus, when consumers perceive that a company fails to uphold ethical standards—like a mismatch between company's actions and ascribed responsibility—, they are more likely to express dissatisfaction through complaints or by switching to an alternative brand. It is therefore reasonable to propose the following hypotheses:

H4: Ascription of responsibility positively predicts intention to switch away from the company.

H5: Company type has an indirect effect (via perceived corporate agency and ascription of responsibility) on switching intentions, with participants being more likely to switch when a protest targets an oil company rather than a bank funding oil projects.

3. Overview of Studies

We conducted two survey experiments to test the extent to which climate activism opposing the expansion of fossil fuel infrastructure was susceptible to a backlash caused by the activists' actions. Study 1 (H1-H5) analyzed whether disruptive protests (relative to moderate protests) targeted at specific companies (oil companies and banks funding oil) undermined perceptions of corporate agency and consumer switching intentions. The proposed hypotheses for Study 1 are depicted in the theoretical model shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1 Theoretical model of Study 1.

Given that financial institutions, particularly banks, play a less evident yet critical role in enabling fossil fuel expansion to continue, Study 2 builds on the findings of Study 1 by examining whether reframing the role of banks as directly responsible for exacerbating climate change can enhance the attribution of agency and mitigate the backfire effects associated with disruptive protests. Thus, Study 2 explores whether the negative effect of disruptive protests on perceived corporate agency persists even after accounting for the banks' role (weak/indirect vs. strong/direct) in enabling fossil fuel expansion, thereby addressing potential confounding factors from Study 1 and reinforcing the robustness of the findings. We manipulated the frame

linking banks and climate change to confirm or discard the following explanation for the results we obtained in Study 1:

H6: Disruptive protests will reduce perceived agency less when the bank's involvement in climate change is portrayed as strong rather than weak.

We obtained ethical approval from the Ethics Committee of the University of (*name anonymized for peer-review*) to conduct the survey experiments, complying with all relevant regulations for research with human participants. We reported all treatment conditions and measures included in the studies. The materials, pre-registration, data, and code used in this research are available as an Open Science Framework permanent archive at:

https://osf.io/dqghu/?view_only=ad3acc1915904ddabdbbf55bbd52b8cd.

4. Study 1

4.1. Sample and Procedure

We recruited a politically balanced sample of 400 participants (200 Democrats and 200 Republicans) from a Prolific online panel of the US population (49.50% female, 49.00% male, 1.50% other, $M_{age} = 44.97$, $SD_{age} = 14.44$). The final sample consisted of 398 participants, 2 of whom were excluded for not completing the survey. The sample's demographic characteristics are reported in Table A.1 in the appendix.

At the beginning of the survey, participants were asked to imagine a scenario where they were scrolling X (formerly known as Twitter). The post is authored by a fictional news agency, Sun News, and describes a protest organized by a fictional environmental activist group, "Green Earth". The description of the protest and the accompanying picture varied depending on the experimental condition (see Fig. A.1- A.4 in the appendix). Participants were randomly

assigned to one of four experimental factor treatments of a 2 (Moderate protest vs. Disruptive protest) \times 2 (Oil company vs. Bank funding oil projects) between-subjects factorial design. The moderate protest involved demonstrations outside the company, while the disruptive protest involved spray-painting the company's premises and erecting barriers that obstructed the entrance for workers. To avoid confounding effects of pre-existing attitudes, companies' brand names were not used and were referred to as a major US bank or oil company.

A manipulation check confirmed that the framings worked as intended. Participants exposed to disruptive protest framings reported significantly higher levels of perceived extremism ($t(396) = -14.707, P < .0001$), disruptiveness ($t(396) = -15.966, P < .0001$), and harmful behaviors ($t(396) = -14.887, P < .0001$) as compared to those exposed to moderate protests. Protests were perceived equally extreme, disruptive and harmful both when targeted at oil companies and at banks funding oil projects. After the corresponding framing was administered to the treatment groups, participants answered an online questionnaire. The study design, data collection method, hypotheses, and planned analyses were pre-registered on AsPredicted (https://aspredicted.org/2JH_HCC).

4.2. Measures

The experimental manipulations were coded as follows: The binary variable "Protest extremity" was assigned a value of 0 for modest protests and 1 for disruptive protests. Similarly, the variable "company type" was coded as 0 when the targeted company was a bank funding oil and 1 when it was an oil company.

In order to measure switching intentions, participants were asked to imagine the company targeted by the protest was their current bank or oil (fuel) supplier and rated on a five-point Likert-type scale (1 = very unlikely to 5 = very likely) how likely it is they would switch to

another company if that was the case. The Perceived agency scale consisted of three items (Tapal et al., (2017) , rated on a five-point Likert-type scale (1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree). The resulting three-item Perceived agency variable was reliable ($\alpha = 0.78$). The Ascription of Responsibility Scale was adapted from the variable used in Stern et al.’s (1999) Value-Belief-Norm Theory of Support for Social Movements ($\alpha = 0.95$). The survey concluded with some demographic questions. See the Appendix for questionnaire items. The full survey in Qualtrics’s format is available at Open Science Framework.

4.3. Results

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics for each experimental group regarding switching intentions. Considering only the direct effect of the experimental manipulations, moderate protests stand out as significantly more effective in increasing switching intentions than disruptive protests. When it comes to company type, however, its effect is more nuanced, and we have to look at its effect on the proposed mediators to have a sense of the indirect effect.

Table 1. Intention to switch to another company, by experimental group.

Company type	Protest extremity	Mean	SD	95% LLCI	95% ULCI
Bank	Moderate	2.77	1.090	2.507	3.028
	Disruptive	2.14	1.189	1.881	2.399
Oil company	Moderate	2.78	1.411	2.521	3.039
	Disruptive	2.33	1.309	2.073	2.594

A t-test was conducted to compare participants’ perceptions regarding a protest targeting an oil company versus a protest targeting a bank financing an oil-and-gas project. We found significant differences in perceived corporate agency ($\Delta = 0.61$, 95% CI [0.43, 0.79], $t(1, 396) = 6.53$, $P < 0.001$, $d = 0.67$, 95% CI [0.47,0.87]) and ascription of responsibility ($\Delta = 0.54$, 95% CI [0.29, 0.78], $t(1, 396) = 4.29$, $P < 0.001$, $d = 0.43$, 95% CI [0.23,0.63]), with the oil company

being attributed higher levels of both constructs compared to the bank funding the oil company's activities – hence providing support for H1, with medium effect sizes. That is, even when both companies were engaged in oil and gas projects, company type (oil company managing the project vs. bank funding it) makes participants perceive oil companies as having higher agency and responsibility.

We conducted a moderated mediation analysis to test whether the indirect effect of company type (oil company vs. bank funding oil) on switching intentions, mediated by perceived agency and ascription of responsibility, varied based on protest extremity (moderate vs. disruptive). A customized "PROCESS" macro v3.5.3 (Hayes, 2017) with bias-corrected 95% confidence intervals (10000 bootstrap samples) was used to test the significance of the indirect effects. A significant index of moderated mediation was used to test the significance of the moderated mediation (i.e., the difference of the indirect effects by protest extremity) was also calculated to confirm whether the moderated mediation was statistically meaningful.

The results showed that the indirect effect of targeting an oil company (vs. bank) on switching intentions, mediated by perceived agency and ascription of responsibility was positive and significant in both the conditions, but stronger in disruptive protest condition ($b_{ind., disruptive} = 0.30$, $SE = 0.06$, 95% CI [0.19, 0.43]) than the moderate protests ($b_{ind., moderate} = 0.12$, $SE = 0.05$, 95% Boot CI [0.03, 0.21]). The significant difference between conditional indirect effects (Moderated mediation index = 0.19, $SE = 0.07$, 95% CI [0.06, 0.33]) confirms that the disruptive protests targeting oil companies increased switching intentions more than moderate protests. This means that the effect of moderate protests on switching intentions is more similar across company types, and differences emerge between oil companies and banks that have suffered disruptive protests. This divergence in the indirect effect between moderate and

disruptive protest is shown by the protest extremity variable significantly moderating the relationship between company type and perceived agency ($b = -0.53$, $SE = 0.17$, $t = -3.05$, $P = 0.002$, 95% CI [0.19, 0.88], $\eta_p^2 = 0.022$) supporting H2 with a small effect size.

Importantly, the diverging effect on perceived corporate agency (Figure 2) is subsequently carried through the mediation process, ultimately influencing switching intentions.

Fig. 2 Conditional effect of protest extremity and company type on the perception of company's agency.

As shown in Figure 3, the lower switching intention for banks can be explained by oil companies being perceived as having higher corporate agency ($b = 0.34$, $SE = 0.13$, $t = -2.64$, $P = 0.009$, 95% CI [0.09, 0.59]), which predicts company's ascription of responsibility for

climate change ($b = 0.73$, $SE = 0.06$, $t = 13.05$, $P < 0.001$, 95% CI [0.62, 0.85]), supporting H3, and with an increase of responsibility positively influencing intention to switch ($b = 0.47$, $SE = 0.05$, $t = 10.07$, $P < 0.001$, 95% CI [0.38, 0.57]) also supporting H4. The moderated mediation model remained robust after controlling for political affiliation.

Fig. 3 Moderated mediation model.

Note: Bootstrapped 95% confidence intervals are provided in parentheses; * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.001$; The indirect effect (dashed-line) is significant because 95% CI doesn't contain zero. Covariate: political affiliation.

The effect size of the mediation was $c'ps = -0.16$, 95% CI [0.10, 0.23])— small but significant effect size, supporting H5. The $c'ps$ is a partially standardized effect size used in mediation-only models, that facilitates the interpretation of the magnitude of the indirect effect, as well as the portion of the effect that operates through the mediators (Hayes, 2017).

Lastly, we conducted a Bonferroni-corrected pairwise comparison of the total effect of company type, analyzing differences by political affiliation and the protest extremity (Figure 4) to ensure our results were robust and that there were no substantial differences between political orientations. Political affiliation did not significantly interact with protest extremity or company type, and the effects on perceived agency and intention to switch remained robust.

The differences between Democrats and Republicans within company types and protest extremity groups were non-significant. While some effects became non-significant after controlling for political affiliation, such as the intention to switch for protests targeting oil companies, overall, the patterns remained consistent across Democrats and Republicans.

Fig. 4 Bonferroni-corrected pairwise comparison of the total effect of disruptive protests, segmented by political affiliation and type of company targeted.

Note. Significant effects are marked as (*). M: mediator. DV: dependent variable.

4.4. Discussion

The purpose of Study 1 was to determine how consumers respond to climate protests based on the extremity of the protest (moderate vs. disruptive) and the type of company involved (oil vs. bank), as well as how these responses shape perceptions of attributional mechanisms, such as

corporate agency and responsibility. Overall, the results support our proposed moderated mediation model and are in line with the framework of attribution theory.

Consistent with our hypotheses, moderate protests were generally more effective than disruptive protests in influencing switching intentions across company types. However, disruptive protests (vs. moderate protests) resulted in higher switching intentions only when the target was an oil company. This pattern was explained by the differences in perceived corporate agency and ascription of responsibility, consistent with attribution theory, because oil companies were consistently seen as having higher agency and responsibility for climate change than banks, which in turn increased consumers' intention to switch.

As anticipated, the attributional effects were moderated by protest extremity, such that when disruptive protests targeted banks, participants perceived them as having less agency. In contrast, when disruptive protests targeted oil companies, that did not reduce perceived agency, and attribution of responsibility remained strong. These findings support core tenets of the attribution theory that individuals are more likely to make dispositional inferences and assign blame based on perceived agency and responsibility when the target is seen as intrinsically responsible. The results remained robust after controlling for political orientation; the negative response to disruptive protests does not appear to be driven by partisan affiliation in this context.

Taken together, these findings have important strategic implications for activists who may highlight the direct financial and enabling role of banks in fossil fuel expansion through their protests. We explore this proposition more directly in Study 2, by experimentally manipulating how the bank's role is framed in media and whether shifting attention from activists to financial institutions influences perceptions. This is an important inquiry because aligning protest

extremity with how consumers perceive company agency seems crucial for avoiding adverse outcomes, such as switching to another company.

5. Study 2

5.1. Sample and Procedure

We recruited a representative sample of 400 participants from a Prolific online panel of the US population (47.70% female, 51.30% male, 1.00% other, $M_{\text{age}} = 45.04$, $SD_{\text{age}} = 15.91$). The final sample consisted of 376 participants, after excluding participants who did not complete the survey or failed an attention check. The sample's demographic characteristics are reported in Table A.2 in the appendix.

As in Study 1, participants are exposed to a social media post about a fictional environmental activist group, *Green Earth*, targeting a major U.S. bank. The content of the protest description and the background details of the accompanying image varied according to the experimental condition. The participants were randomly assigned to one of four conditions in a 2 x 2 between-subjects design: protest extremity (moderate vs. disruptive) and the perceived role of the bank (weak or indirect link vs. strong or direct link). The protest extremity images in the stimuli were depicted similarly to those in Study 1 (see Fig. A.5- A.8 in the appendix). While the bank remained the target across all conditions, its role in climate change was framed differently across conditions, as in the weak/indirect link condition, the protest message stated, “*They (protesters) condemn the company for indirectly supporting the expansion of fossil fuel projects.*” In contrast, in the strong/direct link condition, the message was altered to, “*They (protesters) condemn the company for playing a key role in enabling fossil fuel expansion by*

directly funding and profiting from these projects.” To control for potential biases arising from pre-existing attitudes, no specific company names were mentioned; instead, the bank was generically referred to as *a major U.S. bank*.

5.2. Measures

The experimental manipulations were coded as follows: The binary variable “Protest extremity” was assigned a value of 0 for modest protests and 1 for disruptive protests. Similarly, the variable “link to fossil fuel expansion” was coded as 0 when the connection was weak or indirect, and 1 when the connection to exacerbating climate changes was strong or direct.

For the manipulation check, participants evaluated the extent to which the protest scenario they were exposed to was extreme (1 = not at all extreme to 5 = very extreme), disproportionate (1 = not at all disruptive to 5 = very disruptive), and unjustified (1 = not justified at all to 5 = very justified). As in Study 1, we measured participants’ Perceived Agency ($\alpha = 0.67$) from Tapal et al. (2017), followed by demographic questions. The wording of the questionnaire and the Qualtrics survey flow are available on Open Science Framework.

5.3. Results

As expected, disruptive protests were perceived as significantly more extreme ($\Delta = 1.66$, 95% CI [1.42, 1.91], $t(1, 374) = 13.45$, $P < 0.001$, $d = 1.38$), disproportionate ($\Delta = 1.42$, 95% CI [1.17, 1.68], $t(1, 374) = 11.05$, $P < 0.001$, $d = 1.14$), and unjustified ($\Delta = 0.75$, 95% CI [0.48, 1.02], $t(1, 374) = 5.51$, $P < 0.001$, $d = 0.57$), than moderate protests.

Consistent with Study 1, participants reported a lower perceived agency when the protest was disruptive, compared to when it was moderate ($\Delta = -0.19$, 95% CI [0.01, 0.40], $t(1, 374) = 2.12$, $P = 0.035$, $d = 0.22$, 95% CI [0.02, 0.42])—small effect size. Surprisingly, however,

manipulating the bank’s link to climate change (weak vs. strong) did not significantly increase participants’ perceptions of the bank’s agency ($\Delta = 0.17$, 95% CI [-0.30, 0.53], $t(1, 374) = 0.30$, $P = 0.17$)—thus rejecting H6. Table 2 presents the descriptive statistics for each experimental group.

Table 2. Perception of bank’s agency by experimental group.

Protest extremity	Link to fossil fuel expansion	Mean	SD	95% LLCI	95% ULCI
Moderate	Weak/indirect	3.53	0.75	3.37	3.69
	Strong/direct	3.72	0.76	3.56	3.87
Disruptive	Weak/indirect	3.40	1.04	3.19	3.62
	Strong/direct	3.46	0.92	3.28	3.65

A two-way ANOVA revealed no significant interaction effect between protest extremity and the bank’s link to climate change on perceived agency $F(1, 372) = 0.462$, $P = 0.500$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.001$, although protest extremity had a significant main effect on perceived agency, $F(1,372) = 4.367$, $P = 0.037$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.012$, indicating—in line with Study 1—that disruptive protests led to a greater reduction in perceived agency than moderate protests, regardless of the bank’s link to climate change. In contrast, the bank’s connection to climate change alone did not have a significant main effect on perceived agency, $F(1,372) = 1.834$, $P = 0.177$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.005$.

Bonferroni-adjusted pairwise comparisons showed that, when the bank’s link to climate change was weak, disruptive protests led to no significant reduction in perceived agency ($\Delta = -0.13$, 95% CI [-0.38, 0.13], $F(1, 372) = 0.98$, $P = 0.322$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.003$). In contrast, when the bank’s link to climate change was strong, disruptive protests led to a drop in perceived agency ($\Delta = -0.25$, 95% CI [-0.50, 0.00], $F(1, 372) = 3.88$, $P = 0.050$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.010$).

These results remained robust when controlling for political affiliation and climate change concern. As shown in Figure 5, when the protest was moderate, participants’ perceptions of the

bank's agency were more distinct depending on whether they were in the strong or weak link condition. However, when the protest was disruptive, the bank's link to climate change became less relevant, and perceived agency declined and converged across conditions.

Fig. 5 Conditional effect of protest extremity and link to fossil fuel expansion on the perception of company's agency.

5.4. Discussion

Study 2 examined how protest extremity and the perceived connection between a bank and fossil fuel expansion influence perceptions of the bank's agency. In line with findings from Study 1, disruptive protests led to a significant reduction in perceived agency, suggesting that

the extremity of the protest influences attributions of responsibility toward the bank. While we hypothesized that drawing attention to the bank's active role in financing oil projects would strengthen agency perceptions, our results indicate that protest extremity remains the dominant factor influencing perceived agency. Notably, the bank's direct or indirect link to climate change did not significantly impact perceived agency, nor did it moderate the effect of protest extremity. These findings contribute to the broader understanding of the attribution theory interpretation we proposed by demonstrating that disruptive protest triggers dispositional attributions towards activists rather than situational attribution towards the company. So, rather than increasing perceptions of corporate agency and responsibility, disruptive protests redirect blame onto activists themselves, making the company appear less accountable for its role in climate change—even after manipulating connection to climate change.

This finding has important implications for the interpretation of Study 1. Specifically, the robustness of the protest extremity effect observed in Study 1—regardless of whether the bank was framed by media as playing a direct or indirect role in fossil fuel expansion—emphasizing the bank's link to climate change, however weak or strong, is unlikely to avoid backlash to disruptive protests.

6. General Discussion

Across two studies, the present research investigated how individuals' perceptions—particularly attributions of corporate agency and responsibility—, are influenced by protests against companies and their perceived corporate role in exacerbating climate change. In line with previous research on activism (Brown, 2023; Feinberg et al., 2020), Study 1 found that moderate protests were generally more effective than disruptive protests in encouraging

consumers to shift away from the target company. Notably, disruptive protests were more impactful when the target was an oil company due to heightened perceptions of perceived agency and responsibility. As anticipated, observers attributed less control and responsibility to banks for their climate-related impact. Study 2 followed up on this finding by focusing exclusively on banks and manipulating how their role in climate change was framed (strong vs. weak) by media. Contrary to our expectations, explicitly emphasizing a bank's direct role in fossil fuel expansion did not significantly increase perceptions of its agency. This suggests that protest extremity—rather than framing banks' role in climate-change—drives perceived agency, with moderate protests resulting in higher perceived agency than disruptive protests.

Both studies underscore the critical role of perceived agency in shaping participants' reactions to climate protests. However, the reduction in perceived agency due to disruptive protests was more pronounced for banks than for oil companies (Study 1). Even when media narratives explicitly framed banks as central to fossil fuel expansion, disruptive protests still diminished perceptions of banks' agency (Study 2). These findings are in line with the paradoxical situation we theoretically envisioned: while disruptive protests can increase awareness of companies' environmental harm, they may also risk diminishing attributions of corporate agency—and hence fail to pressure or boycott companies—, when the targets are financial institutions. In the case of banks, moderate protests may be more effective; in contrast, when it comes to oil companies, protest extremity appears to have less impact on perceived agency, likely because their environmental harm is so evident that their responsibility remains salient even during disruptive protests, as shown in Study 1. Overall, these findings align with attribution theory by demonstrating that protest type and target interact to shape blame attributions, which in turn influence consumer intentions to switch.

Theoretical and Practical Implications

Our findings are in line with the tenets of Attribution theory by showing that individuals tend to assign more responsibility and feel more compelled to take action—such as switching companies—when the targeted company is perceived as having higher agency and a direct role in causing climate change. This research further expands the application of the theory by suggesting that disruptive protests seem to shift the locus of attribution from dispositional blame directed at the companies to situational blame placed on activists. This shift in where individuals place blame can manifest, for example, as someone being exposed to a moderate protest and thinking “*The company knows what it’s doing and is clearly responsible for the environmental harm*” whereas someone exposed to a disruptive protest might instead think, “*Activists went too far and their actions were disproportionate, so maybe the company isn’t as responsible as they claim.*”

Importantly, the effect of disruptive protests is more pronounced when the perceived causal link between the target and the issue is less visible, as in the case of banks. It also appears that simply highlighting the company’s role in financing fossil fuel projects contributing to climate change is insufficient to counteract the negative effects of disruptive protests. One possible explanation is that perceptions of corporate agency may be more strongly shaped by other factors, such as corporate messaging, policy commitments, or broader systemic understandings of financial institutions’ roles in climate change (Yang et al., 2018). Given our finding in Study 2 that consumer perceptions toward companies targeted by disruptive protests are relatively resistant to reframing, we provide preliminary evidence—subject to further validation—that constructing stronger causal narratives does not necessarily enhance attributions of agency.

Previous studies on social mobilization against energy infrastructure have emphasized that energy transitions are not merely technological but are deeply intertwined with stakeholder voice and social dynamics (Gomez-Carrasco & Michelon, 2017) . Addressing the concerns of activists, therefore, requires increasing social acceptance and acknowledging the implications of companies' actions towards stakeholders. For activists, adopting a strategic approach to protesting is essential. If the protest target does not have direct links to fossil fuel production, then moderate protest tactics may be more effective in enhancing perceptions of corporate agency and avoiding public backlash.

While divestment is often a primary demand of activists, financial institutions should proactively communicate their sustainability-linked financial decisions to position themselves as responsible actors rather than reacting to activist pressure. While banks may enjoy more ambiguity in their perceived role in climate change, this buffer is fragile and contingent upon public perception of responsibility. CSR messaging that emphasizes long-term decarbonization efforts, investments in sustainable technologies, and a strategic transition toward renewable energy can help shape public perceptions of corporate agency, while reducing activist pressure. By doing so, banks can counteract perceptions of inaction in addressing climate change and reinforce their image as responsible actors with agency (Dahlmann et al., 2019).

In this regard, moderate protests present opportunities for constructive dialogue and stakeholder engagement; in response, companies should emphasize their progress toward climate goals rather than discrediting the protests. This approach shifts public focus toward CSR initiatives rather than activist tactics. Conversely, in the case of disruptive protests, companies should implement effective reputation management strategies. Adopting excessive or repressive responses (e.g., see “the stick”; Wasow, 2020) may inadvertently increase public sympathy for

activists and shift scrutiny onto corporate actions, potentially undermining the company's credibility.

7. Limitations and Future Research

An obvious limitation of our studies is that we only captured participants' immediate reactions upon learning about climate protests. To draw more definitive conclusions, a longitudinal approach would have been necessary, enabling us to determine whether our findings align with those of Ostarek et al. (2024), who found that the negative effect of disruptive protests diminishes over time and public support may become positive in the long term—a finding we cannot confirm nor reject in this case. In addition to temporal limitations, our findings are geographically specific to the United States, where disruptive climate activism is seen as marginal (McAdam, 2017). In contrast, recent research in Germany found that climate strikes and civil disobedience actually garnered support and increased public concern about climate change (Brehm & Gruhl, 2024), a result that contrasts with our U.S.-based findings.

Study 1 utilized a politically balanced convenience sample of U.S. participants recruited via Prolific (see Table A.1 in the appendix), which may limit the generalizability of the findings. However, it is worth noting that our sample sizes were adequate, addressing a shortcoming in recent research on climate activism, where some studies have been underpowered (e.g., Badullovich, 2024). The generalizability of these findings is also limited because the media attention garnered by disruptive protests (even negative) is highly complex and cannot be deterministically linked to their effects. The salience of media coverage over time may influence the importance people give to news, based on agenda-setting theory (Pollach, 2014).

Another potential concern is the use of fictional environmental agency, scenarios, and news media to illustrate disruptive protests. This was a deliberate choice to avoid confounding factors such as familiarity with the brand or media; in real life, these factors indeed influence the way information is processed (Chen et al., 2023). Notably, the realism of the protest scenarios presented is underscored by the fact that an actual protest against a major U.S. bank, closely mirroring our manipulation—including the tactic of blocking entrances and spray painting (Bautzer, 2023) took place after data collection for Study 1. For study 1, the selection of type of image for each condition were motivated by actual news coverage of events (a protestor spray painting, protestors holding placards, protestors cutting up cards), however, it is plausible that the manipulations we used may lead respondents to react more strongly to certain conditions and interpret them as a social norm. Since this effect would be independent of the perceived severity of the protest, in Study 2, this limitation was addressed to ensure uniformity of images and texts other than specific manipulation.

Lastly, it is important to interpret our conclusions about the effectiveness of protests with caution. Our study focused on very specific measures and did not aim to provide a comprehensive assessment of protest effectiveness. Our research only narrowly considered constructs related to customer loyalty and perceptions of agency and responsibility, and did not account for other dimensions in which disruptive protests may be effective, such as the potential for these actions to build bonding capital among group members—which often results from the preparation and strong internal relationships required for such actions.

8. Conclusion

While moderate protests generally foster greater public support and direct attribution of responsibility to the target company, we showed that disruptive protests can backfire—and end up being less effective than moderate tactics—, particularly if the company's role in the climate crisis appears to be indirect (e.g., banks funding oil projects). Therefore, for individuals seeking to engage in effective activism without directly confronting the system, alternative forms of “insider” climate activism (Skoglund & Böhm, 2022) may offer a more viable approach. These strategies, which focus on accelerating the energy transition working within the existing system rather than opposing it outright (Yang et al., 2018), may be less likely to backfire.

This research extends the application of attribution theory to corporate social responsibility, demonstrating that disruptive protests function as attributional cues that shift perceptions from corporate accountability to the behavior of the activists themselves. Our findings suggest that disruptive protests can alter responsibility attributions, regardless of a company's actual role in exacerbating climate change. Notably, shifts in dispositional attributions—and the ensuing changes in public opinion—are more pronounced when banks are the targets of disruptive protests. In contrast, when oil companies are targeted, these shifts are less likely to occur, as their environmental harm is widely recognized. As a result, even if observers disapprove of activists' methods or consider their protests too extreme, they continue to hold oil companies primarily responsible for the climate crisis. These insights have important implications for climate activists, corporate crisis management, and the broader discourse on corporate accountability in addressing climate change.

Our findings highlight the market and reputational consequences of misaligned protest dynamics. Consumer switching intentions represent a tangible business risk in addition to brand image. For companies, particularly those working behind the scenes of extractive industries, passive invisibility is no longer a viable shield. Instead, corporations should engage in proactive transparency through environmental reporting that aligns with sustainability pathways (Caputo et al., 2021).

In the context of the ongoing climate crisis, companies face a critical decision: whether to resort to greenwashing tactics to manipulate external perceptions or to adopt credible emissions reduction strategies (Dahlmann et al., 2019). Rather than focusing solely on protecting their public image and avoiding boycotts, firms should prioritize managing public relations in a way that genuinely reflects their commitment to achieving net-zero targets.

References

- Ali, S. M. A., & Gill, D. A. (2022). Media Framing and Agenda Setting (Tone) in News Coverage of Hurricane Harvey: A Content Analysis of the New York Times, Wall Street Journal, and Houston Chronicle from 2017 to 2018. *Weather, Climate, and Society*, 14(2), 637–649. <https://doi.org/10.1175/WCAS-D-21-0009.1>
- Badullovich, N., Tucker, D., Amoako, R., Ansah, P., Davis, B., Horoszko, U., Zakiyyah, H., & Maibach, E. (2024). How does public perception of climate protest influence support for climate action? *Npj Climate Action*, 3(1), 1–3. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44168-023-00096-9>
- Bautzer, T. (2023, April 24). Climate activists spray protests on U.S. bank offices on eve of annual meetings. *Reuters*. <https://www.reuters.com/world/us/climate-activists-spray-protests-us-bank-offices-eve-annual-meetings-2023-04-24/>
- Brehm, J., & Gruhl, H. (2024). Increase in concerns about climate change following climate strikes and civil disobedience in Germany. *Nature Communications*, 15(1), 2916. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-024-46477-4>
- Brown, J. M. (2023). Civil Disobedience, Sabotage, and Violence in US Environmental Activism. In J. L. Sowers, S. D. VanDeveer, & E. Weinthal (Eds.), *The Oxford Handbook of Comparative Environmental Politics* (pp. 356–364). Oxford University Press.
- Caputo, F., Pizzi, S., Ligorio, L., & Leopizzi, R. (2021). Enhancing environmental information transparency through corporate social responsibility reporting regulation. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 30(8), 3470–3484. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.2814>
- Chen, K., Molder, A. L., Duan, Z., Boulianne, S., Eckart, C., Mallari, P., & Yang, D. (2023). How Climate Movement Actors and News Media Frame Climate Change and Strike: Evidence from Analyzing Twitter and News Media Discourse from 2018 to 2021. *The International Journal of Press/Politics*, 28(2), 384–413. <https://doi.org/10.1177/19401612221106405>
- Chenoweth, E., & Stephan, M. J. (2011). *Why Civil Resistance Works: The Strategic Logic of Nonviolent Conflict*. Columbia University Press.
- Comyns, B., Meschi, P.-X., & Norheim-Hansen, A. (2023). Firms' responses to environmental misconduct accusations under the condition of contested practice complexity: Evidence from the palm oil production industry. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 32(8), 5332–5348. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.3419>
- Dahlmann, F., Branicki, L., & Brammer, S. (2019). Managing Carbon Aspirations: The Influence of Corporate Climate Change Targets on Environmental Performance. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 158(1), 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-017-3731-z>

- Davis, C. (2022, October 26). *Are Just Stop Oil's dramatic art museum protests hurting their own cause?* CNN. <https://www.cnn.com/style/article/just-stop-oil-protests-the-conversation/index.html>
- Erb, T., Perciasepe, B., Radulovic, V., & Niland, M. (2022). Corporate Climate Commitments: The Trend Towards Net Zero. In M. Lackner, B. Sajjadi, & W.-Y. Chen (Eds.), *Handbook of Climate Change Mitigation and Adaptation* (pp. 2985–3018). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-72579-2_146
- Estes, N. (2024). *Our History Is the Future: Standing Rock Versus the Dakota Access Pipeline, and the Long Tradition of Indigenous Resistance*. Haymarket Books.
- Feinberg, M., Willer, R., & Kovacheff, C. (2020). The activist's dilemma: Extreme protest actions reduce popular support for social movements. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, *119*(5), 1086–1111. <https://doi.org/10.1037/pspi0000230>
- Fisher, D. R., & Nasrin, S. (2021). Climate activism and its effects. *WIREs Climate Change*, *12*(1), e683. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.683>
- Fishman, E. J., & Husman, J. (2017). Extending attribution theory: Considering students' perceived control of the attribution process. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, *109*(4), 559–573. <https://doi.org/10.1037/edu0000158>
- Foreman, D. (1993). *Confessions of an Eco-Warrior*. Crown.
- Gause, M., & Oguh, C. (2024, June 28). *Climate activists arrested after protest at Citi's New York headquarters*. Reuters. <https://www.reuters.com/world/us/climate-activists-plan-protests-citis-new-york-headquarters-2024-06-28/>
- Ginder, W., Kwon, W.-S., & Byun, S.-E. (2021). Effects of Internal–External Congruence-Based CSR Positioning: An Attribution Theory Approach. *Journal of Business Ethics*, *169*(2), 355–369. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-019-04282-w>
- Golen, J. (2024, June 23). *Six climate protesters run onto 18th green and spray powder, delaying finish of PGA Tour event*. AP News. <https://apnews.com/article/travelers-championship-intruders-18th-hole-police-bc3e9408e9417b8520fe866795761fe2>
- Gomez-Carrasco, P., & Michelon, G. (2017). The Power of Stakeholders' Voice: The Effects of Social Media Activism on Stock Markets. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, *26*(6), 855–872. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.1973>
- Gustafson, A., Goldberg, M. H., Kotcher, J. E., Rosenthal, S. A., Maibach, E. W., Ballew, M. T., & Leiserowitz, A. (2020). Republicans and Democrats differ in why they support renewable energy. *Energy Policy*, *141*, 111448. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2020.111448>
- Harvey, P., Madison, K., Martinko, M., Crook, T. R., & Crook, T. A. (2014). Attribution Theory in the Organizational Sciences: The Road Traveled and the Path Ahead. *Academy of Management Perspectives*, *28*(2), 128–146. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amp.2012.0175>

- Hayes, A. F. (2017). *Introduction to mediation, moderation, and conditional process analysis: A regression-based approach*. Guilford Press.
<https://www.guilford.com/books/Introduction-to-Mediation-Moderation-and-Conditional-Process-Analysis/Andrew-Hayes/9781462534654>
- Heider, F. (1944). Social perception and phenomenal causality. *Psychological Review*, *51*(6), 358–374. <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0055425>
- Heider, F. (1958). The naive analysis of action. In F. Heider (Ed.), *The psychology of interpersonal relations* (pp. 79–124). John Wiley & Sons Inc.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/10628-004>
- Kelley, H. H. (1967). *Attribution theory in social psychology*. Nebraska symposium on motivation.
- Kelley, H. H. (1973). The processes of causal attribution. *American Psychologist*, *28*(2), 107–128. <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0034225>
- McAdam, D. (2017). Social Movement Theory and the Prospects for Climate Change Activism in the United States. *Annual Review of Political Science*, *20*(Volume 20, 2017), 189–208. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-polisci-052615-025801>
- McGreal, C. (2021, October 26). *Revealed: 60% of Americans say oil firms are to blame for the climate crisis*. The Guardian.
<https://www.theguardian.com/environment/2021/oct/26/climate-change-poll-oil-gas-companies-environment>
- Mitchell, S. (2024, August 14). *Activists Are Bringing the Heat to the Banks Funding Climate Crisis*. Truthout. <https://truthout.org/articles/activists-are-bringing-the-heat-to-the-doorstep-of-banks-funding-climate-crisis/>
- Noor, D. (2024, May 21). *Top oil firms' climate pledges failing on almost every metric, report finds*. The Guardian. <https://www.theguardian.com/us-news/article/2024/may/21/oil-companies-report-fossil-fuels-climate>
- Noor, D. (2025, June 18). Youth-led Sunrise Movement to launch campaign to ‘villainize big oil’ and force climate action. *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com/us-news/2025/jun/18/sunrise-movement-big-oil-climate-bills>
- Ostarek, M., Rogers, C., Klein, L., Thomas-Walters, L., & Özden, J. (2024). *The short and long-term impacts of disruptive animal rights protest*. Social Change Lab.
https://www.socialchangelab.org/_files/ugd/2ed91c_3d9954a301de481680054dba3ea21ad.pdf
- Piazza, A., & Perretti, F. (2020). Firm behavior and the evolution of activism: Strategic decisions and the emergence of protest in US communities. *Strategic Management Journal*, *41*(4), 681–707. <https://doi.org/10.1002/smj.3116>
- Pollach, I. (2014). Corporate Environmental Reporting and News Coverage of Environmental Issues: An Agenda-Setting Perspective. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, *23*(5), 349–360. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.1792>

- Shoemaker, P. J. (1982). The perceived legitimacy of deviant political groups: Two experiments on media effects. *Communication Research*, 9(2), 249–286.
- Skoglund, A., & Böhm, S. (2022). *Climate Activism: How Communities Take Renewable Energy Actions Across Business and Society*. Cambridge University Press.
- Stern, P. C., Dietz, T., Abel, T., Guagnano, G. A., & Kalof, L. (1999). A Value-Belief-Norm Theory of Support for Social Movements: The Case of Environmentalism. *Human Ecology Review*, 6(2), 81–97. JSTOR. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/24707060>
- Tamborini, R., Grall, C., Prabhu, S., Hofer, M., Novotny, E., Hahn, L., Klebig, B., Kryston, K., Baldwin, J., Aley, M., & Sethi, N. (2018). Using Attribution Theory To Explain The Affective Dispositions Of Tireless Moral Monitors Toward Narrative Characters. *Journal of Communication*, 68(5), 842–871. <https://doi.org/10.1093/joc/jqy049>
- Tapal, A., Oren, E., Dar, R., & Eitam, B. (2017). The Sense of Agency Scale: A Measure of Consciously Perceived Control over One’s Mind, Body, and the Immediate Environment. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 8. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2017.01552>
- Temper, L., Bene, D. del, & Martinez-Alier, J. (2015). Mapping the frontiers and front lines of global environmental justice: The EJAtlas. *Journal of Political Ecology*, 22(1), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.2458/v22i1.21108>
- Valenzuela, L. M., Mulki, J. P., & Jaramillo, J. F. (2010). Impact of Customer Orientation, Inducements and Ethics on Loyalty to the Firm: Customers’ Perspective. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 93(2), 277–291. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-009-0220-z>
- Vestergaard, A., & Uldam, J. (2022). Legitimacy and Cosmopolitanism: Online Public Debates on (Corporate) Responsibility. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 176(2), 227–240. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-020-04703-1>
- Vogelsong, S. (2020). What sank the Atlantic Coast Pipeline? It wasn’t just environmentalism. *Virginia Mercury*. <https://virginiamercury.com/2020/07/08/what-sank-the-atlantic-coast-pipeline-it-wasnt-just-environmentalism/>
- Wasow, O. (2020). Agenda Seeding: How 1960s Black Protests Moved Elites, Public Opinion and Voting. *American Political Science Review*, 114(3), 638–659. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S000305542000009X>
- Weiner, B. (1985). An attributional theory of achievement motivation and emotion. *Psychological Review*, 92(4), 548–573. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-295X.92.4.548>
- Williams, G. (2019). Regulation Enables: Corporate Agency and Practices of Responsibility. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 154(4), 989–1002. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-018-3896-0>
- Yang, A., Uysal, N., & Taylor, M. (2018). Unleashing the Power of Networks: Shareholder Activism, Sustainable Development and Corporate Environmental Policy. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 27(6), 712–727. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.2026>

- Young, K. A., & Thomas-Walters, L. (2024). What the climate movement's debate about disruption gets wrong. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, *11*(1), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-023-02507-y>
- Zou, H. L., Zeng, R. C., Zeng, S. X., & Shi, J. J. (2015). How Do Environmental Violation Events Harm Corporate Reputation? *Business Strategy and the Environment*, *24*(8), 836–854. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.1849>

Tables

Table 1. Intention to switch to another company, by experimental group.

Company type	Protest extremity	Mean	SD	95% LLCI	95% ULCI
Bank	Moderate	2.77	1.090	2.507	3.028
	Disruptive	2.14	1.189	1.881	2.399
Oil company	Moderate	2.78	1.411	2.521	3.039
	Disruptive	2.33	1.309	2.073	2.594

Table 2. Perception of bank's agency by experimental group.

Protest extremity	Link to fossil fuel expansion	Mean	SD	95% LLCI	95% ULCI
Moderate	Weak/indirect	3.53	0.75	3.37	3.69
	Strong/direct	3.72	0.76	3.56	3.87
Disruptive	Weak/indirect	3.40	1.04	3.19	3.62
	Strong/direct	3.46	0.92	3.28	3.65

Figure legends

Fig. 1 Theoretical model of Study 1.

Fig. 2 Conditional effect of protest extremity and company type on the perception of company's agency.

Fig. 3 Moderated mediation model.

Fig. 4 Bonferroni-corrected pairwise comparison of the total effect of disruptive protests, segmented by political affiliation and type of company targeted.

Fig. 5 Conditional effect of protest extremity and link to fossil fuel expansion on the perception of company's agency.

Appendix A: Supplementary Information

Disruptive Climate Protests Against Companies: Analyzing Customer Perceptions in an Experimental Setting

Participants' demographics

Table A.1 Characteristics of the sample used in Study 1 (N = 400).

Sample characteristics		Frequency	Percentage
Political affiliation	Democrat	200	50.0%
	Republican	200	50.0%
Gender	Female	198	49.5%
	Male	196	49.0%
	Other	6	1.5%
Age	19-25	30	7.5%
	26-34	82	20.6%
	35-44	98	24.6%
	45-54	72	18.1%
	55-64	76	19.1%
	> 65	40	10.1%
Household income	< \$19,999	35	8.8%
	\$20,000–\$39,999	75	18.8%
	\$40,000–\$59,999	72	18.0%
	\$60,000–\$79,999	65	16.3%
	\$80,000–\$99,999	52	13.0%
	\$100,000–\$149,999	55	13.8%
	> \$150,000	37	9.3%
<i>"I prefer not to say"</i>	9	2.3%	
Education	No formal qualifications	3	0.8%
	Secondary education (e.g., GED)	5	1.3%
	High school diploma	95	23.8%
	Technical/community college	66	16.5%
	Undergraduate degree	161	40.2%
	Graduate degree	57	14.2%
	Doctorate	9	2.2%
<i>"I prefer not to say"</i>	4	1.0%	

Table A.2 Characteristics of the sample used in Study 2 (N = 393).

Sample characteristics		Frequency	Percentage
Political affiliation	Democrat	115	29.3%
	Republican	114	29.0%
	Independent	164	41.7%
Gender	Female	201	47.7%
	Male	187	51.3%
	Other	4	1.0%
Ethnicity	White	232	61.7%
	Black	43	11.4%
	Asian	30	8.0%
	Mixed	40	10.6%
	Other	30	8.0%
Age	19-25	55	14.0%
	26-34	64	16.3%
	35-44	70	17.9%
	45-54	65	16.6%
	55-64	89	22.7%
	> 65	48	12.2%
Household income	< \$19,999	35	8.9%
	\$20,000–\$39,999	76	19.4%
	\$40,000–\$59,999	68	17.3%
	\$60,000–\$79,999	58	14.8%
	\$80,000–\$99,999	43	11.0%
	\$100,000–\$149,999	54	13.8%
	> \$150,000	54	13.8%
	<i>“I prefer not to say”</i>	4	1.0%
Education	No formal qualifications	2	0.5%
	Secondary education (e.g., GED)	10	2.6%
	High school diploma	86	21.9%
	Technical/community college	66	16.8%
	Undergraduate degree	137	34.9%
	Graduate degree	78	19.9%
	Doctorate	12	3.1%
	<i>“I prefer not to say”</i>	1	0.3%

Measures of Study 1

In order to measure switching intentions, participants were asked to imagine the company targeted by the protest was their current bank or oil supplier and rated on a five-point Likert-type scale (1 = very unlikely to 5 = very likely) how likely it is they would switch to another company if that was the case. In the bank group we asked, “*Imagine finding out that the bank these protesters are targeting is your current bank. How likely is it that you would switch to another bank?*”, and in the oil company group we asked, “*Imagine that the oil company these protesters are targeting owns the gas station you use for fuel. How likely is that you would switch to another provider?*”.

The Perceived agency scale was adapted from Tapal et al. (2017) and consisted on three items: “*The decision of whether to invest in new oil-and-gas is within the company’s hands*”, “*This company is completely in control of everything that results from its new oil-and-gas investment projects*”, and “*This company’s new oil-and-gas investment decisions are planned from the very beginning to the very end*”. These statements were rated on five-point Likert-type scales (1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree). The resulting three-item Perceived agency variable was reliable ($\alpha = 0.78$).

The Ascription of responsibility scale was adapted from the variable used in Stern et al.’s (1999) Value-Belief-Norm Theory of Support for Social Movements. Participants rated on five-point Likert-type scales (1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree) the extent to which they agreed with the following statements: “*This company is jointly responsible for the exhaustion of energy sources*”, “*This company is jointly responsible for global warming*”, and “*This company is jointly responsible for the environmental problems caused by the extraction and use of oil*”. The resulting three-item Ascription of responsibility variable was reliable ($\alpha = 0.95$).

As for the manipulation check, participants rated the extent to which the protest scenario they were exposed to was extreme (1 = not at all extreme to 5 = very extreme), disruptive (1 = not at all disruptive to 5 = very disruptive) and harmful (1 = not at all harmful to 5 = very harmful).

Manipulation

Study 1

At the beginning of the survey, participants were asked to imagine a scenario where they were scrolling X (formerly known as Twitter) and came across a post about a protest against a recently proposed oil exploration project. The post is authored by a fictional news agency, Sun News and describes a protest organized by a fictional environmental activist group, “Green Earth”. The description of the protest and the accompanying picture varied depending on the experimental condition: Participants were randomly assigned to one of four experimental factor treatments of a 2 (Moderate protest vs. Disruptive protest) \times 2 (Oil company vs. Bank funding oil exploration) between-subjects factorial design.

Fig. A.1 Moderate protest against oil company

Fig. A.2 Moderate protest against bank

Fig. A.3 Disruptive protest against oil company

Fig. A.4 Disruptive protest against bank

Members of the environmental organization Green Earth engaged in a demonstration by spray painting the premises of a 'major US bank' and erecting barriers, effectively obstructing the entrance for company personnel. Protesters oppose funding of new oil exploration projects that negatively impact emissions reduction goals. [#NoNewOil](#).

12:00 PM · Jun 1, 2023

230 Retweets 445 Quote Tweets 654 Likes

Study 2

Study 2 employed a 2×2 between-subjects survey experiment, in which participants were randomly assigned to one of four experimental conditions. Each condition presented participants with a social media-like post depicting a protest scenario. The experimental design varied along two dimensions: (1) the perceived role of the bank in exacerbating climate change (weak vs. strong connection) and (2) the extremity of the protest (moderate vs. disruptive).

There were some variations in the descriptions of protest actions in Study 1, such as the use of different images, that were not accounted for. To enhance experimental control, these distinctions were minimized in Study 2. All textual elements remained identical except for the manipulated variables, and all images were standardized to depict the same main protest scene. The only variation in the images pertained to the background elements, where banners appeared in the moderate protest condition and spray paint appeared in the disruptive condition, aligning with the descriptions provided in the corresponding social media posts.

Fig. A.5 Moderate protest against bank with weak connection to climate change

Fig. A.6 Moderate protest against bank with strong connection to climate change

@thesunnews

Members of the environmental organization Green Earth engaged in a peaceful demonstration outside a 'major US bank'. Protesters oppose investments in new oil exploration projects that negatively impact emissions reduction goals. They condemn the company for playing a key role in enabling fossil fuel expansion by directly funding and profiting from these projects. #NoNewOil

2:10 PM · Jan 30, 2025 · **3.5K** Views

53 Retweets **25** Quotes **525** Likes **3** Bookmarks

Fig. A.7 Disruptive protest against bank with weak connection to climate change

Fig. A.8 Disruptive protest against bank with strong connection to climate change

References

- Stern, Paul C., Thomas Dietz, Troy Abel, Gregory A. Guagnano, and Linda Kalof. 1999. "A Value-Belief-Norm Theory of Support for Social Movements: The Case of Environmentalism." *Human Ecology Review* 6 (2): 81–97. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/24707060>.
- Tapal, Adam, Ela Oren, Reuven Dar, and Baruch Eitam. 2017. "The Sense of Agency Scale: A Measure of Consciously Perceived Control over One's Mind, Body, and the Immediate Environment." *Frontiers in Psychology* 8. <http://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2017.01552>.